

Evaluation of Knowledge, Treatment Beliefs and Psychological Impact of Acne Vulgaris in Patients Attending BIMS Hospital: A Cross Sectional Study

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Abstract:

Background: Acne vulgaris is a chronic inflammatory disease affecting majority of the adolescent population with a considerable impact on the psychosocial well-being of a person.

Aim: 1) To assess the psychological impact of acne vulgaris. 2) To analyse their beliefs about acne and outlook about treatment of acne.

Materials and Methods: This was a cross sectional study conducted at a tertiary government hospital involving 448 cases of acne, who were analyzed using a predesigned questionnaire and Cardiff acne disability index (CADI).

Results: Out of 448 cases 220 were males and 228 were females. 210 cases diagnosed with grade 2 acne and 173 replied they had acne on and off. In spite of this 228 cases had never taken any treatment in past. Of the 220 cases who had taken treatment, 91 cases had been treated by a dermatologist and 60 cases had taken treatment based on a friend's suggestion. Only 53 replied that cost is immaterial. 158 patients preferred using only night cream. 321 were aware that dermatologist was the qualified person to treat acne. 80 subjects had CADI scores > 8 indicating significant psychological impact and 368 showed < 8 score, implying no psychological impact.

Conclusion: This study shows that the psychological impairment due to acne is not so severe in our set up compared to other reports. It is important to take into account the cost of therapy and counsel adequately regarding the mode of therapy while treating acne which can improve the compliance and outcome.

Keywords: Acne vulgaris, Psychological impairment, Cardiff acne disability index (CADI).

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Introduction

Acne is a chronic inflammatory disease of the pilosebaceous units, with multifactorial etiology and pleomorphic lesions in the form of comedones, papules, pustules, nodules and cysts which may even lead to scarring. Studies show that more than 85% of the teenagers, as well as some adults [1] are affected with acne vulgaris. Acne vulgaris is most common skin problem in adolescents, although lesions can appear as early as age 8. [2] Although acne is more common and more severe in boys than girls, it usually occurs in girls at an earlier age and tends to last longer, sometimes into adulthood. [3] The psychological impairment due to acne vulgaris is comparable with certain chronic diseases like

asthma, epilepsy, diabetes and arthritis. [4] Acne patients are prone to low self-esteem, low confidence and social dysfunction which may lead to anxiety, depression, obsessive compulsiveness, embarrassment, psychosomatic symptoms including pain, discomfort and sometimes suicidal ideation. [5] Acne vulgaris patients have higher unemployment compared to those without acne. [6] Assessing quality of life in acne patients will give an insight of the psychological impact of acne which in turn can help provide patients with better services, by acknowledging their real needs and interfering with treatment decisions. There are effective therapies for acne and administration of

these can lead to an improvement in quality of life and psychological health. Increased awareness and early intervention for the psychological and psychiatric sequelae of acne can benefit the patient. This study would impress upon the practitioner the need to thoroughly discuss and counsel the patient with regard to their psychological concern, the expected duration of therapy, adherence to therapy and most importantly the fact that, acne is very well treatable and person's skin may be restored to a near normal state.

Aims of the study:

1. To evaluate the knowledge, treatment beliefs of patients with acne vulgaris.
2. To study the psychological impact on patients suffering from acne vulgaris.

Method of Collection of Data

Patients with acne attending dermatology OPD in BIMS hospital Belagavi were enrolled for study after taking informed consent and interviewed in detail regarding history, symptoms and clinically evaluated to ascertain the diagnosis of acne vulgaris before including them in the study. Acne vulgaris patients were graded using Indian grading system⁷ which was classified into four grades as follows.

Grade 1: Comedones, occasional papules.

Grade 2: Papules, comedones, few pustules.

Grade 3: Predominant pustules, nodules, abscesses.

Grade 4: Mainly cysts, abscesses, widespread scarring.

CADI is a questionnaire which is specific for acne and contains 5 questions-related to the feelings, interference with social life, interaction with opposite gender, avoidance of public places, appearance of the skin and perceived severity of disease state in the last one month.

Each question is scored from 0-3 leading to a total score of 0-15. A CADI score <8 was considered to have a small effect on quality of life and a score >8 as having a larger effect on QOL. [8]

Patients were clinically graded according to the Indian grading system. [7] The clinical grades were correlated with CADI scores as well as a pre-designed questionnaire containing 12 questions to assess the patient's knowledge, beliefs, treatment satisfaction and expenses towards acne.

Inclusion criteria: a) Acne vulgaris cases aged 14-25 years

Exclusion criteria:

- Severe systemic diseases.
- Patients on steroids/OCP.
- Acneiform eruption.
- Patients developing acne only in the premenstrual period
- Clinically suspected cases PCOS.

Results:

Table 1: Socio-demographic profile

1. Age group	Study population
14-20 years	297(66.2%)
21-25 years	151(33.7%)
2. Sex	
Male	220(49.1%)
Female	228(50.8%)
3. Occupation	
Students	414(92.4%)
Skilled workers	13(2.9%)
Unskilled workers	21

Table 2: Grading and duration of acne vulgaris patients

1. Acne grading	Number
Grade I	156(34.8%)
Grade II	210(46.8%)
Grade III	72(16%)
Grade IV	10(2.2%)
2. Duration	
<3 month	81(18.1%)
3month-1year	56(12.5%)
>1year	138(30.8%)
On & Off	173 (38.6%)

Table 3: Attitude and Treatment beliefs of acne vulgaris patients

1. Taken treatment	Study population
Yes	220(49.3%)
No	228(50.6%)
2. Sources of treatment who were treated previously	220
Treated by a Doctor	121 (90- by dermatologist, 30-non dermatologists)
Other sources(friend suggestion, social media, over counter products)	99
3. Satisfied with treatment	220
Yes	90(40.9%)
No	130(59.1%)
4. Cost spent for therapy	220
<INR 300	99(45%)
INR 300-600Rs	61(27.7%)
INR 600 -1000Rs	41(18.6%)
INR>1000	19(8.6%)
5. willing to spend cost for therapy	
INR<300	151(33.9%)
Up to INR 500Rs	141(31.4%)
Up to INR 1000Rs	46(10.2%)
Cost doesn't matter	110(24.5%)
6. preference of therapy	
Night cream only	158(35.2%)
Night and day cream only	127(28.3%)
Creams as well as tablets	117(26.1%)
Medical therapy plus Lasers or chemical peels	46(10.2%)

Table 4: Knowledge about acne amongst the subjects

1. Right person to treat acne	Study population
Themselves	54(12%)
Doctor next door	61(13.6%)
Beautician	11(2.4%)
Skin specialist	321(71.6%)
2. Acne is	
Health problem	136(30.5%)
Cosmetic Problem	174(38.8%)
Psychological problem	66(14.7%)
Not a problem	72(16%)
3. Causes of acne	
Hereditary	68(12.2%)
Poor hygiene	106(19.1%)
Hormonal	249(44.9%)
Infection	131(23.6%)
4. Aggravating factors for acne	
High fat diet	120(21.2%)
Cosmetics	101(17.9%)
Weather change	150(26.5%)
Stress	193(43.2%)

Table 5: CADI questions

i) As a result of having acne, during the last month have you been aggressive, frustrated or embarrassed?	
Very much indeed	43(9.5%)
A lot	95(21.2%)
A little	204(45.5%)
Not at all	106(23.6%)
ii) Do you think that having acne during the last month interfered with your daily social life, social events or relationships	

with members of the opposite sex?	
Severely affected	24(5.3%)
Moderately affecting	82(18.3%)
Occasionally	125(27.9%)
Not at all	217(48.4%)
iii) During the last month have you avoided public changing facilities or wearing swimming costumes because of your acne?	
All the time	33(7.3%)
Most of the time	74(16.5%)
Occasionally	95(21.2%)
Not at all	247(55.1%)
iv) How would you describe your feelings about the appearance of your skin over the last month?	
Very depressed and miserable	78(17.4%)
Usually concerned	143(31.9%)
Occasionally concerned	151(33.7%)
Not bothered	76(16.9%)
v) Please indicate how bad was your acne to feel individually	
The worst	37(8.2%)
A major prob	140(31.3%)
A minor prob	205(45.7%)
Not a prob	70(15.6%)

Table 6: CADI analysis in study population

CADI Score	Study population
>8	80(17.8%)
<8	368(82.1%)
Total	448

Discussion

Acne vulgaris is perhaps the most common dermatological condition being treated by dermatologists. In spite of a high prevalence there are lot of misconceptions about this condition. In our study we have tried to find the common beliefs, various modalities of treatment and the extent of psychological impact acne vulgaris can have on a patient.

Our study revealed that most of the patients had grade 2 acne (46.8%) which is similar to a study by Samantha H et al. [8] This shows that patients are worried about their acne and seek medical care at earlier stages. A study by Tallad TM, et al [9] showed that grade 4 acne was more common, which differs from our study. In our study majority (66.2%) of the participants belonged to the age group 14-20 years and it may be because adolescents are more concerned about their appearance and the most commonly affected age group, which is similar to a study by Burton et al [10] and Jancovic et al [11].

Females (50.8%) outnumbered males (49.1%) by a narrow margin. This trend is slightly different from other studies and perhaps indicates the rising trend of cosmetically conscious men. Which is similar to a study by Ismail, [12] Eleni Tasola et al [13] and Tallad TM et al [9] in which the majority of the study population was constituted by females. In a

study by Ibrahim A et al [14] males outnumbered females which differs from our study. (92.4%) of our study populations were students and stress (43.2%) was the most common aggravating factor for acne. Studies by Hyunk Hoon Kwon et al [15], Green Sinclair et al, [16] Tan et al [17] and Ibrahim A et al. [14] showed similar results. This could be easily explained by the fact that acne is an adolescent disease and the over anxious parents pressurizing their children for improvement of their scholastic performance and the constant need to have a perfect skin as endorsed by celebrities. A small number of respondents felt weather (26.5%) and cosmetic (17.9%) could aggravate acne. Considering these things, the results of acne being an on and off phenomenon in most of the respondents was proved consistent. These results were in contrast with study by Tan et al [17] and Samantha H et al [8] who reported that majority of study population had acne for more than one year.

The majority of our study population was educated and had a fair amount of awareness about acne. Most of the cases felt that hormones were the predominant cause for acne and ironically, also felt acne was a cosmetic problem rather than a health problem. They had the awareness that dermatologist was the right person to treat acne. A small portion interestingly also felt that even a beautician could treat acne and some even

responded that they could treat their acne by themselves. We wonder if there was an element of sarcasm in the reply, since they were responding at a skin clinic and had come to seek treatment for acne. Study by Tan et al [17], Ibrahim et al [14] and Poli et al [18] reported infection (18%), diet (72.1%), poor hygiene(67.8%) to be predominant cause for acne in their studies respectively, which is not the same in our study. More than half of our study population had never sought any form of treatment. This can be attributed to various reasons, since the study was done in a government hospital, this class of patients were probably ignorant about their looks. The same could also be due to low economic conditions. Since many subjects also felt it was only a cosmetic problem, they didn't find it to be a hindrance in their daily activities and delayed seeking treatment.

In our study, majority preferred only a night cream for their acne. Whether this was a reflection of their spending mentality or a matter of convenience was unclear. This was an important revelation as many doctors still believe in prescribing a range of oral and topical medications. If the mindset of patients is not kept in mind, it would lead to unnecessary rise in the overall cost of treatment and would also lead to poor adherence to therapy. It would be important to counsel patients on how long to use, how much to use and consequences of over and under usage of the acne medications to ensure adherence to treatment. Our study shows that majority were willing to spend only INR <300 per month. This finding could stem from the fact that this study was conducted in a tertiary government hospital where the strata of patients mostly belong to low income group. This finding along with the fact that most cases had acne only on and off leads us to believe that it would be good to have combi packs containing anti acne preparation, sunscreen and facewash of smaller quantities with a price tag of INR<300. This would improve the compliance and also minimize the possible side effects. In our study 220(49.1%) subjects had taken treatment previously, out of which 121(55%) took treatment as per doctor's prescription. Even after consulting doctors for their problem only 53 were explained about available treatment options, preferred mode of therapy, cost effectiveness and duration of therapy. This finding emphasizes on the need for adequate counseling to ensure adherence to the treatment.

In our study >50% of previously treated patients were unhappy with the treatment they had received. Only 90 participants were satisfied with their treatment and this number coincides with the number of study population treated by dermatologists (91).

In our study we used Cardiff Acne Disability Index (CADI) to assess the psychological impact of acne

vulgaris. Out of 448, 80(17.8%) subjects had CADI scores > 8, indicating a psychological impact due to acne and 368(82.1%) had scores <8 implying there was no psychological impact. Our study showed that the psychological impact due to acne is not as severe as compared to other studies. It might be because of the place where we conducted the study, which is a government tertiary care hospital where most of the outpatients are usually from the low to mid socio-economic status. Also one of the questions pertaining to wearing swimming costumes (Q 3 of CADI) may not be relevant in our set up. Wearing revealing clothing is regarded as a luxury quotient which again becomes void in our set up. Studies by Samanthula H et al, [8] Hanisha et al, [19] and Ibrahim A et al [14] showed that their patients suffered from psychological impact which was contradictory to our study.

Conclusion

- This study shows that the psychological impairment due to acne is not as severe as compared to other reports.
- This study will stress the importance on the part of the treating physician about the proper discussion and counseling of the patient with regard to the available treatment modalities, expected duration of each modality of therapy and importance of adherence to therapy. Most important fact is that treating doctor should explain to the patient that acne is treatable condition and person's skin may be restored to a near normal state.
- It is important to take into account the cost factor and mode of therapy while treating acne.

Recommendations

1. This study suggests that misconceptions and false beliefs on acne were widespread. This is our responsibility and duty as a doctor to educate them through community based programmes and mass media to improve and promote health services.
2. In India only few studies were done to know the Psychological impact in acne vulgaris patients compared to western countries. More large scale, defined population studies are required to conclude the psychological impact of acne.

Limitations of Our Study:

1. No defined study population was considered in our study like students or educated population etc. We had considered only the age group. Study population was selected randomly among those patients who attended the dermatology OPD of Belagavi Institute of Medical Sciences Hospital Belagavi with presenting complaints of acne during the study period.
2. In our study we have not correlated severity of acne with its psychological impact.

3. Socio economic status was not taken into consideration which would have helped to decide the preferred therapeutic modality as per the affordability of the participants.

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